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AIRPORT: A CATALYST FOR A CARBON NEUTRAL AVIATION

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Introduction

The airport sector is undergoing a profound transformation driven by the urgent need to address climate change and environmental sustainability. Airports, as strategic hubs of global mobility, play a crucial role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting more sustainable operational practices, not only within their own infrastructure but throughout the entire aviation value chain.

This paper explores the main challenges airports face in their decarbonization journey, analyzing the most effective strategic levers to reduce emissions and overall environmental impact.

Special attention is given to establishing prioritization criteria for implementing various actions, aiming to guide informed and sustainable decision-making.

A specific focus is dedicated to the concrete experience of an Italian airport, providing a tangible example of how strategies can translate into operational interventions and measurable results.

Furthermore, the paper considers the fundamental role of financial and regulatory incentives in accelerating the transition toward a low-impact airport management model, while highlighting key barriers that may slow this process.

The work concludes with reflections on opportunities and key actions to consolidate a sustainable growth path in the airport sector, emphasizing the importance of shared commitment among all involved stakeholders

1. Challenges facing airports

Aviation is facing a set of highly specific challenges in its journey toward carbon emissions reduction. While public perception often suggests that the sector accounts for around 10% of global emissions, data from 2019 shows that the aviation industry was responsible for less than 3% of global CO₂ emissions. When factoring in the broader climate effects of other greenhouse gases and aviation-related phenomena—captured under the term *Effective Radiative Forcing (ERF)*—the figure rises to approximately 3.5%

This gap between public perception and scientific evidence highlights a communication challenge that adds to the sector's existing technical and operational hurdles. Unlike other hard-to-decarbonize industries, such as cement production or road freight, aviation currently lacks a simple or breakthrough technological solution capable of eliminating or drastically cutting emissions in the near term. This makes decarbonization efforts even more complex, especially in a global context where demand for air travel continues to grow steadily.

Given this landscape, a coordinated effort across all components of the sector is essential. Airports, airlines, technology providers, and regulatory authorities must work together, leveraging a broad array of innovative strategies and solutions. Airports, in particular, play a pivotal role in aviation's sustainability pathway. They are not only gateways for travelers, but also critical infrastructure providers and key connectors between the many actors within the airport ecosystem—airlines, service providers, and public institutions.

When it comes to managing direct and indirect emissions related to purchased energy—commonly referred to as *Scope 1* and *Scope 2* emissions—many airports have already taken meaningful action. Common initiatives include electrifying ground support vehicles, improving energy efficiency, and switching to renewable energy providers. These actions are enabled by widely available technologies and represent an essential first step in reducing environmental impact.

However, these direct and energy-related emissions account for only a small fraction of the total. At airports with advanced sustainability programs, around 95% of emissions fall under *Scope 3*—indirect emissions from sources not directly controlled by the airport. These are primarily generated by third-party activities, most notably aircraft operations such as taxiing, takeoff, landing, and approach. Because these emissions make up the vast majority, it's vital that airports expand their decarbonization efforts to include these areas in order to achieve significant reduction.

Currently, over 200 airports worldwide are engaged in emissions accreditation programs, such as the *Airports Council International (ACI)* "Airport Carbon Accreditation scheme". These programs involve measuring and tracking emissions from aircraft movements, surface access transport, and business travel, and they promote active engagement with third parties. This integrated approach reflects a growing recognition within the airport sector of the need to address its broader environmental footprint.

Beyond carbon emissions, airports must also contend with other critical environmental challenges. Local air quality is a key concern—especially emissions of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and fine particulate matter—which can directly affect the health of surrounding communities. Aircraft noise and biodiversity protection in nearby areas are additional factors that must be carefully considered in any sustainability plan.

While there are numerous potential strategies for reducing Scope 3 emissions, they vary greatly in terms of implementation complexity and actual environmental benefit.

In-depth studies, carried out in partnership with airports and specialized consultancies, have helped identify practical and impactful levers that can enable airports to make substantial progress toward decarbonization in the coming years.

2. Core decarbonization strategic levers

Given that *Scope 3* emissions account for the largest share of an airport's total environmental impact—and considering the significant progress already made in reducing direct emissions (*Scope 1*) and energy-related emissions (*Scope 2*)—this chapter focuses on the most effective levers for addressing *Scope 3* emissions. Four key areas of intervention have been identified:

- Aircraft operations;
- Passenger and employee ground transportation;
- Airport infrastructure construction and maintenance;
- Handling operations.

1. Aircraft operations

The majority of *Scope 3* emissions stem from aircraft fuel consumption, both from main engines and auxiliary power units (*APUs*). To reduce overall fuel use, airports must re-evaluate their operational procedures and work closely with other stakeholders—such as air navigation service providers (*ANSPs*) and airlines—to implement best practices across the board.

Airports can adopt data-driven strategies to optimize aircraft stand allocation or deploy innovative technologies like taxi-bots, developed by companies such as *IAI*, *TLD*, and *Airbus*. Although these systems are currently certified only for narrow-body aircraft, versions for wide-body planes are under development.

Another critical aspect is *APU* fuel use, which powers onboard systems such as air conditioning while the aircraft is parked at the gate. This consumption can be significantly reduced through the use of ground power units (*GPUs*), which have a lower fuel footprint and can often be electrically powered.

To encourage airlines to adopt such technologies, airports should consider collaborative cost-saving models, such as offering "*GPU-as-a-service*" solutions, sharing the financial benefits of reduced fuel consumption

GPU operations – Geneva Airport

For several years, Geneva Airport has implemented a system that directly supplies aircraft with electricity, heating, and cooling via ground power units (GPUs). This system enables aircraft to avoid using their auxiliary power units (APUs), a mandatory requirement imposed by the airport.

The adoption of GPUs has proven extremely effective in reducing CO₂ emissions associated with landing, take-off, and taxi (LTO) operations. Specifically, analysis shows how this solution can cut Scope 3 emissions related to this flight phase by nearly 10%. This is a significant achievement, considering that Scope 3 emissions typically constitute the majority of an airport's environmental footprint.

Beyond the environmental benefits, using GPUs also brings relevant economic advantages for airlines. APUs require regular maintenance based on usage hours, often necessitating temporary aircraft downtime for servicing. Therefore, GPU usage reduces both emissions and the need for APU maintenance, consequently decreasing aircraft grounding times. This translates into greater operational efficiency and lower costs for airlines.

Because *Scope 3* emissions are intrinsically linked to airline operations, airports must actively promote and incentivize measures that help carriers reduce fuel usage. Key areas include the adoption of next-generation aircraft, increased use of *Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF)*, optimized takeoff and landing procedures, and more efficient taxiing practices

Fleet renewal – Geneva Airport

Geneva Airport has launched a dedicated program to incentivize the use of the latest generation aircraft. This initiative aims to significantly reduce environmental emissions.

Thanks to the program, each replaced aircraft contributes to a 40% reduction in noise and a 15% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to older models. Project costs are shared, with approximately CHF 818,000 specifically allocated to CO₂ emission reduction.

In 2022, the airport's total emissions related to air traffic (excluding some Scope 3 emissions) amounted to 1.1 million tons of CO₂. The average for each aircraft movement, calculated between 2010 and 2022, stands at 9.25 tons of CO₂, with a margin of error of $\pm 3\%$.

Considering that new generation aircraft account for approximately 25% of scheduled and charter flights, the program has enabled an estimated reduction of about 41,000 tons of CO₂, corresponding to a 4.7% increase in sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) usage. This saving comes at almost half the cost of an equivalent reduction achieved through certified carbon offsets (Gold Standard).

If the number of flights with new generation aircraft continues to grow at the projected annual rate of 10% (currently estimated at 27%), the program could achieve a CO₂ reduction equivalent to a 13% SAF addition by 2030, almost double the target set by the *European RefuelEU* regulation.

The implementation of *Airport Collaborative Decision-Making (A-CDM)* systems is another powerful tool to enhance overall operational efficiency and minimize emissions both in the air and on the ground.

These efforts not only reduce CO₂ emissions but also yield substantial co-benefits, including decreased noise pollution and lower levels of local particulate matter.

2. Passengers & Employees transport

A significant portion of an airport's total emissions comes from the ground travel of passengers and employees to and from the facility. This makes ground mobility a strategic area for intervention, especially through the promotion of more sustainable transportation options.

A key strategy involves shifting from private internal combustion vehicles (gasoline or diesel) to public transport or electric vehicles (EVs). The emissions reduction potential is considerable, with EVs producing 60–90% fewer emissions than conventional cars, depending on the local energy mix.

To be effective, airports must collaborate with local authorities and transit agencies to improve access via public transport. Solutions may include buses, trams, or trains—ideally electric-powered and low-emission options like light rail and metro systems, as electric buses are not yet widely adopted.

Public transport usage can be further encouraged by enhancing passenger convenience, for example by decoupling luggage and passenger transport through remote check-in at urban rail stations or other mobility hubs. For airport staff, measures such as subsidized transit passes or discounted fares—potentially extendable to tourists—can incentivize public transport adoption.

Sustainable mobility – Geneva Airport

Geneva Airport has long implemented a sustainable mobility plan aimed at reducing private car usage among its employees. The goal is to eliminate parking for those who can easily commute to work by public transport, with an exemption for staff working outside regular service hours. Out of approximately 11,000 employees, over 7,000 work irregular hours; for these individuals, the airport has activated dedicated free transport services, which are also utilized by passengers with early morning flights.

In 2022, the program cost CHF 2.1 million, roughly half the cost of building new parking facilities. Environmentally, the initiative is estimated to have avoided up to 1,850 tonnes of CO₂ annually, considering average distances traveled and emissions from new cars. This figure could be even higher when including passengers served by the special transport.

The program directly contributes to the objectives of the Swiss Sectoral Aviation Infrastructure Plan, which aims to increase the public transport usage share among employees and passengers to 44% and 58% respectively.

At the same time, airports should invest in EV charging infrastructure. The availability of charging stations is essential for large-scale EV uptake. Slow (AC) chargers can be installed for employee parking, while fast (DC) chargers should be placed near terminals for passengers and taxis. Some airports have introduced mandatory use of electric taxis or offer discounted parking rates for EVs.

Finally, micromobility options—such as electric bikes and scooters—can offer sustainable commuting alternatives for airport personnel. While these modes are less practical for passengers due to luggage constraints, they provide a low-impact solution for short-distance travel in urban settings.

3. Infrastructure

Construction activities account for approximately 13% of an airport's annual emissions. It is therefore essential to minimize new construction wherever possible and to reduce the environmental impact of necessary developments. Optimizing the use of existing infrastructure is a top priority, supporting growth without new builds. This could involve improving operational efficiency, repurposing current facilities, or renovating and modernizing buildings to extend their lifespan.

When new construction is unavoidable, efforts should focus not only on reducing CO₂ emissions but also on minimizing impacts related to water usage, waste, and biodiversity. Using low-impact or recycled materials—such as sustainable cement and steel—is crucial. New buildings should aim for environmental certifications, such as DGNB in Germany, and be designed for high structural efficiency to limit long-term resource consumption.

Sustainable construction – Oslo Airport

Oslo Airport stands as a prime example of how airport infrastructure can be expanded while adhering to strict environmental sustainability criteria.

One of the project's key aspects was the use of low-carbon building materials. Notably, recycled steel and concrete were employed, while load-bearing structures were built using wood sourced from FSC-certified forests. Furthermore, integrating a geothermal system allowed for efficient heating and cooling of interior spaces with minimal environmental impact.

The project achieved BREEAM Excellent certification, one of the highest recognitions for sustainable building in Europe. According to estimates, the new terminal wing resulted in a reduction of over 35,000 tonnes of CO₂ compared to an infrastructure built with traditional methods.

This initiative demonstrates how it's possible to combine the need for airport infrastructural development with the goal of curbing emissions and promoting responsible building practices.

Partnering exclusively with construction firms that follow eco-friendly practices—ideally those certified under ISO 14000—further reinforces sustainability objectives.

4. Handling operations

Ground handling is a strategic, yet often overlooked, area for emissions reduction. It includes all services provided to aircraft while on the ground—such as baggage handling, refueling, catering, pushback, climate control, and power supply.

Traditionally, these operations rely heavily on diesel-powered vehicles and fossil fuel-based portable generators, contributing significantly to Scope 1 and Scope 3 emissions, as well as to local air and noise pollution.

To address this, many airports are transitioning to fully electric ground handling systems. Investments are being made in zero-emission equipment such as baggage carts, pushback tractors, conveyor belts, cargo lifts, and electric generators. This shift not only directly reduces CO₂ and pollutant emissions but also improves air quality in operational zones and lowers equipment maintenance costs.

Handling operators – Swissport

Swissport has adopted an ambitious environmental strategy aiming to electrify at least 55% of its ground support equipment fleet by 2032, a target that rises to 100% in countries with readily available infrastructure. In some of its most advanced bases, such as Geneva, Zurich, and Oslo, Swissport has already converted a significant portion of its operational fleet to electric vehicles and has installed rapid charging stations near ramp areas. Concurrently, the company has progressively phased out the use of aircraft auxiliary power units (APUs) for parked aircraft, replacing them with Ground Power Units (GPUs) and fixed air conditioning systems. This significantly contributes to reducing local emissions and improving air quality on airport aprons.

Swissport's approach isn't limited to simply acquiring electric vehicles. It also encompasses staff training, the digitalization of processes, and active collaboration with the airports where it operates, positioning it as a key player in the sustainable transformation of the ground handling sector. This model highlights how partnerships between private operators and airport authorities are crucial for achieving a large-scale and effective transition towards low-emission aviation.

3. Prioritisation matrix

As previously discussed, airports have several 'levers' at their disposal to reduce their environmental impact. However, each lever differs significantly in terms of both potential impact and ease of implementation—making it essential for airports to establish clear priorities.

This analysis aims to assess each lever according to these two factors, helping airports understand where to focus their efforts to effectively reduce their environmental footprint. The findings reveal clear trends across four main categories of intervention:

1. Aircraft operations levers

These levers offer the greatest potential to reduce environmental impact, as aircraft operations account for a significant share of airports' indirect (Scope 3) emissions. Many of these measures are also relatively easy for airports to implement and should therefore be prioritized.

- **Fleet renewal and new operational procedures:** encouraging airlines to modernize their fleets and adopt new operating practices has the highest environmental impact and is relatively simple to enforce. Airports can accelerate the transition to next-generation aircraft by offering incentive-based fee structures, while new operational procedures can be directly mandated by the airport;
- **Taxiing and idle time optimization:** optimizing ground taxiing phases and aircraft idle time is another high-impact measure that can be implemented through straightforward airport-level regulations;
- **Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) infrastructure:** although more complex to deploy in the short term, developing SAF infrastructure is critical for the decarbonization of flight operations and should be actively supported by airports. Additional infrastructure may be required to transport SAF to the airport (especially if a kerosene pipeline is not in place to reduce overall carbon impact), though final delivery can rely on existing systems since SAFs are "drop-in" fuels (i.e., compatible with current infrastructure).

2. Transport levers

These solutions can bring significant environmental benefits, but come with much greater implementation challenges than aircraft-related measures.

- **Improving public transport connectivity:** enhancing connections to public transportation can have a substantial impact, but requires convincing local authorities and transit agencies to invest additional funds—resulting in longer timelines and more complex stakeholder dynamics;
- **Support electric vehicle (EV) adoption:** encouraging and incentivizing the use of EVs is complex due to the number of stakeholders involved (including utility companies and national governments), and charging infrastructure within the airport often remains a secondary concern;
- **Micromobility:** micromobility options (e.g., scooters, e-bikes) are much easier to implement but provide significantly lower environmental benefits, given their limited ability to replace more polluting transport modes.

3. Construction levers

These interventions should be integrated opportunistically into the airport's broader planning process. Their environmental impact tends to be lower overall, and implementation challenges are primarily linked to long planning cycles and significant regulatory hurdles. When undertaking new construction or renovation projects, airports should prioritize the use of low-carbon materials and maximize the reuse of existing infrastructure.

4. Handling operation levers

Handling-related measures (covering activities like baggage loading/unloading, refueling, and aircraft assistance) focus on reducing the environmental impact of ground support operations and equipment. Although the overall impact may be lower than aircraft operations (which drive most *Scope 3* emissions), this is an area where airports have more direct control and can achieve tangible reductions in their operational carbon footprint.

However, this often requires significant investments in new equipment—such as the electrification of *Ground Support Equipment (GSE)*—as well as the development of appropriate charging infrastructure. While these changes can be managed internally or coordinated with ground handlers, they still require financial commitment.

On the other hand, optimizing procedures (e.g., reducing idle times, improving routing) can be achieved through staff training and smarter management systems. These require lower upfront investment than equipment upgrades but depend on strong operational coordination. Key barriers include high initial costs to renew the GSE fleet and the need to align efforts across multiple handling operators working at the airport.

Source: Roland Berger

3.1. Case Study – Milan Bergamo Airport

In the global landscape of sustainability efforts, *Milan Bergamo Airport* (BGY), managed by SACBO, stands out for its proactive approach to decarbonization. Since 2019, it has been a signatory of ACI EUROPE’s “*NetZero2050 Resolution*”, committing to achieving net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050.

In May 2024, the airport submitted its formal Net-Zero Roadmap to ACI EUROPE—a strategic document that goes beyond declarations of intent by translating the concept of “decarbonization levers” into concrete, measurable actions. The roadmap outlines a clear and ambitious path to reach carbon neutrality well before mid-century.

The following table is a graphical representation of the Net-Zero 2050 Roadmap:

Source: BGY International Service

This framework serves as a practical application of the previous discussion on decarbonization levels: each “*Improvement Measure*” listed is, in effect, a specific lever the airport intends to activate. The plan focuses primarily on reducing direct (*Scope 1*) and indirect emissions from energy generated (*Scope 2*), outlining clear actions, their scope, and implementation timelines. The nature of each measure is also identified, distinguishing between *Optimization* and *Innovation*: the former indicates a measure to improve the efficiency of existing processes; the latter involves the introduction of new technologies/solutions. This is a truly operational strategy, ideal for achieving the goal of net-zero CO₂ emissions well before 2050.

The Milan Bergamo example demonstrates how high-level sustainability concepts can be translated into actionable, measurable plans. These are essential for guiding airports toward achieving their ambitious carbon neutrality goals. It is through a combination of technological innovation, process optimization, and ongoing commitment that the airport sector can make a concrete contribution to a more sustainable future.

4. What SACBO BGY is doing

Milan Bergamo Airport (BGY), under the management of the SACBO Group, has been seen to proactively engage with the challenges posed by climate change and environmental sustainability, recognizing its crucial role within the broader air transport ecosystem. The actions undertaken by SACBO form part of a holistic strategy that goes beyond mere regulatory compliance and aims for continuous improvement in environmental performance.

Its initiatives are defined by precise policies aimed at managing and mitigating significant impacts across various environmental areas:

1. Energy consumption & Climate change

It has been extensively discussed how airport operations generate significant greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions—direct, indirect from purchased energy, and other indirect emissions along the value chain—that contribute to global warming.

SACBO is aware of the risks associated with dependence on fossil fuels and climate policies. These risks may be operational, such as damage to infrastructure, operational disruptions, increased maintenance costs due to extreme weather events and high temperatures; and financial, including rising compliance costs, reduced traffic due to short-haul flight bans, and loss of certifications like ACA. Opportunities to improve efficiency and reduce long-term costs lie solely in energy transition and technological innovation.

The primary goal remains achieving net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 through the implementation of the aforementioned Net-Zero 2050 Roadmap—a decarbonization plan including concrete actions such as:

- **Energy efficiency:** implementation of smart LED lighting technology and adoption of heat pumps and electric boilers for sanitary hot water;
- **Renewable energy,** such as the installation of photovoltaic systems on parking areas;
- **Vehicle electrification:** complete electrification of the Ground Support Equipment (GSE) fleet via the BASE project (*Bergamo Air Side Electrification*);
- **Biofuel:** use of biofuels as a temporary solution for immediate CO₂ reduction.

SACBO's and BGYIS's Quality, Safety, and Environmental Policies place special emphasis on energy efficiency and minimizing negative impacts. The Net Zero Roadmap 2050 is fully aligned with the principles of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the SDGs, and the Paris Agreements

2. Pollution

Within the context of the Impact, Risk, and Opportunity (IRO) analysis related to pollution, it emerged that the Group's activities—both as an airport operator and through airlines and other value chain actors—can negatively affect air quality in surrounding areas. If not properly controlled, atmospheric emissions may cause public health problems and increase pressure from local communities.

Exceeding regulatory emission limits also poses economic sustainability risks, including potential sanctions, compliance costs, and revenue losses due to operational restrictions. There is also reputational risk.gbb

Potential environmental impacts from accidental spills of chemicals used in airport operations—such as fuels, oils, and antifreeze—that could contaminate soil and water have been considered. Ineffective

storage or fueling management by handlers might jeopardize business continuity and incur additional remediation and emergency management costs.

SACBO adopts a systematic evaluation approach through Environmental Analysis to identify critical issues and priority intervention areas. Periodic air quality monitoring campaigns are conducted; 2024 analyses did not highlight local criticalities.

Water monitoring plans cover wastewater, surface water, groundwater, and runoff waters, with results compliant with regulatory limits. Soil is monitored biannually near fuel storage areas (interstitial gases) to prevent contamination.

The integrated Management System adopted by SACBO includes specific Environmental Procedures that define responsibilities, controls, monitoring, and containment actions. SACBO also promotes responsible behavior among suppliers and companies operating on behalf of both entities.

3. Biodiversity & Ecosystems

The SACBO Group places great value on balancing operational efficiency with safeguarding the surrounding territory, recognizing the interdependence between its activities and the environmental context. The general environmental commitment implies awareness of potential risks to local flora and fauna stemming from operations and infrastructural expansion.

This commitment translates into a structured approach that assesses the feasibility of employing the best available technologies to minimize negative environmental impacts. Systematic environmental analysis and periodic management system reviews aim to identify and address emerging significant environmental aspects, indirectly contributing to ecosystem protection

Gruppo SACBO attribuisce grande valore all'equilibrio tra l'efficienza delle operazioni aeroportuali e la salvaguardia del territorio circostante, riconoscendo l'interdipendenza tra le proprie attività e il contesto ambientale. L'impegno generale nella tutela ambientale implica la consapevolezza dei potenziali rischi per flora e fauna locali derivanti dalle operazioni e dall'espansione infrastrutturale.

4. Resource use and Circular economy

This topic concerns impacts related to resource consumption (such as water and energy) and waste generation. Inefficient management can lead to waste, increased costs, and negative environmental impacts. Opportunities lie in optimizing resource use, reducing waste, and implementing circular economy practices that can generate operational efficiencies and environmental benefits.

SACBO's policies include programs aimed at naturally reducing energy consumption and containing pollution, generally minimizing negative environmental impacts. Attention to EU Taxonomy includes mapping activities connected to the transition towards a circular economy (e.g., building demolition, road and highway maintenance, contaminated site remediation). This indicates a commitment to lifecycle management of materials and valorization of waste.

Value chain relationships play a central role in promoting a shared policy of sustainable and responsible development, which also encompasses efficient resource management.

5. Incentives to accelerate decarbonization

In the context of decarbonization strategies and reducing environmental impact in the airport sector, the inherent limitations of airport taxes to incentivize the reduction of noise or CO₂ emissions can be effectively overcome through the implementation of targeted financial incentives.

Case Study – Geneva Airport

Geneva Airport stands as a prime example of this approach, having introduced incentive schemes, particularly concerning landing fees, to promote the adoption of new generation aircraft.

These agreements, negotiated with airlines and the regulatory body and formalized in 2020, stipulate, for instance, that an airline increasing its share of movements with latest-generation aircraft (from 10% to 30%) can benefit from a 30% reduction in its landing fees.

This initiative has already yielded tangible results: in 2022, nearly 25% of airport movements involved new generation aircraft, with a projected increase to 32% for 2023.

This example clearly demonstrates how airports can actively address *Scope 3* emissions, which represent a significant portion of the sector's overall carbon footprint. However, adopting such schemes requires airports to pursue a more balanced approach between financial performance and ecological performance concerning all emissions (*Scope 1, 2, and 3*). This means carefully evaluating the benefits of environmental investments (such as noise insulation programs) relative to the overall financial costs and the airport's operational obligations.

Consequently, such an approach will require full support from shareholders, as it may involve a temporary reduction in financial performance in favor of long-term sustainable growth.

Therefore, airports hold a strategic position to facilitate achieving "net zero" in aviation, both by encouraging airlines to modernize their fleets with next-generation aircraft and by promoting the use of public transportation to and from the airport through infrastructural improvements and more competitive fare policies for passengers.

6. Key barriers

On the path toward achieving "net zero" and reducing emissions in the airport sector, particularly regarding the challenging *Scope 3* emissions, airports face a series of significant barriers. These challenges require a joint effort from all stakeholders, both internal and external, and a financial commitment that often must be balanced with other operational priorities. Overcoming these obstacles involves action across areas ranging from aircraft operations within and around the airport, to managing passenger and employee transport, to infrastructure development.

1. Influence over domains outside direct control

The first barrier lies in the need for airports to influence areas beyond their direct jurisdiction or control. Taking action in these domains can be problematic, as it may be perceived as undue interference by involved stakeholders such as airlines, public transport networks, construction companies, or industry associations. For example, measures aimed at encouraging the use of next-generation aircraft might be seen by airlines as an attempt by the airport to influence their route planning or fleet usage. Therefore, the effectiveness of such indirect approaches depends on careful design and ongoing monitoring.

2. Contradictory government policies

Airports often find themselves at the center of partially conflicting government policies balancing economic development, land use planning, public health policies, and environmental protection. Although long-term government support is crucial for implementing robust sustainability measures, the priorities among these policies can vary significantly depending on the ruling government. Changes in government priorities represent a complex barrier to overcome, making the continuity of long-term commitments uncertain.

3. Need for financial investments and shareholders alignment

All decarbonization and sustainability actions require significant investments from airports, inevitably impacting their financial results. While costs can potentially be integrated into airport fees, this could reduce their effectiveness due to regulations and the need for acceptance by all airlines. Therefore, it is essential that shareholders and airport management are fully aligned on the long-term sustainability value of the infrastructure. They must agree that such investments contribute to maintaining the airport's long-term operating license, which may require revising short-term financial performance expectations to favor sustainable growth. It is thus crucial to define key strategic objectives, such as an evidence-based target date for achieving net zero, levels of public transport usage, and environmental impact reduction goals.

To overcome these barriers, it is imperative that all measures are presented and discussed transparently with the airport's main stakeholders in order to address the concerns of each organization.

7. Conclusions

The decarbonization process for airports represents both a complex challenge and a significant opportunity. To effectively contribute to the aviation sector's "net zero" goal and meet stakeholder expectations, it is essential that airports strategically reflect on several key areas.

- ❖ Airports must determine where to focus their environmental efforts. While the decarbonization levers previously discussed should be prioritized, it is crucial to recognize that the financial investment and time required to implement many of these measures are substantial and vary significantly depending on the local context. Therefore, airports need to carefully assess which measures will be the most effective and feasible for their specific situation.
- ❖ Implementing any measure inevitably involves costs. Airports must establish clear priorities in decarbonization planning and define financing strategies. It is essential to engage owners and stakeholders (including customers) to ensure strategic alignment and support for the investments needed to uphold corporate social responsibility. Airports should work closely with airlines and other key players to ensure that costs, revenues, and mitigated expenses (e.g., through savings on ETS credits) are fairly distributed across the entire airport ecosystem.
- ❖ Special attention must be given to mitigating the risk of "carbon leakage" (emissions relocation). Selected levers should aim to reduce emissions throughout the entire aviation ecosystem, not only within the airport's direct control. Initiatives focused on fleet renewal present the highest risk of leakage, as limited application could simply shift older aircraft to other routes. Actions related to passenger transport and construction are less susceptible to this risk.
- ❖ Another key area of uncertainty concerns the future refueling infrastructure needed to support airlines' decarbonization ambitions and comply with regulatory mandates. In the short term, the focus is clearly on SAF (Sustainable Aviation Fuel) transport; however, in the long term, airports must seriously consider the need for significant investments in hydrogen infrastructure and refueling, depending on technological developments and airline interest.
- ❖ Finally, it is crucial that airports effectively communicate their decarbonization efforts to the public. Since the aviation sector faces increasing pressure for rapid decarbonization, it is vital to inform the public about concrete actions taken by the ecosystem to fulfill its "social contract." Airports, as key interfaces, play a fundamental role in maintaining public acceptance of air transport by demonstrating that the industry, despite its limited share of global emissions (less than 10%), is taking concrete action.

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